

Thermochemistry of Copper(II)-Tyrosinate in t-Butanol-Water and Glycerol-Water Mixtures at 25°

SYAMAL BANDYOPADHYAY** and SHYAMAL K. SARKAR*

Department of Chemical Technology, Calcutta University, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 25 March 1996, revised 30 October 1996, accepted 5 February 1997

Amino acids are biologically important compounds and have been used as model compounds for understanding the thermodynamic behaviour of proteins. The role of metal ions in preferential complex formation with sites on virus proteins and in such complicated systems has not been well understood. However, by a studying the equilibria between metal ions and amino acids, an insight into the matter can be had. With the recent development of computer programs¹⁻³ for refining equilibrium constant values, it has become possible to examine the contributions of hydrolysed metal ions and complexes, poly nuclear complexes and metal ion protonated ligand complexes in metal-amino acid complex systems.

Although various thermodynamic data are available for the formation of amino acid complexes in aqueous medium, knowledge of the thermodynamic data in mixed solvents is still lacking. Such studies will throw light on the solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions on the thermodynamic parameters. Moreover, direct calorimetry has been used by relatively few researchers to examine the solution thermodynamics of amino acids. Thornton and Skinner⁴ determined the enthalpies of reactions of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} with glycine, serine, threonine and histidine in aqueous medium. Stack and Skinner⁵ determined the heats of formation of chelates of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} with glycine in water. Gergely *et al.*⁶ determined the enthalpies of formation as also stability constants of Cu^{II}-tyrosinate in aqueous medium. Further, Gergely and Kiss⁷ determined the stability constant of Cu^{II}-tyrosinate in water-dioxan mixtures. Letter and Bauman⁸ also determined the formation constant and enthalpy of formation of Cu^{II}-tyrosinate in aqueous medium. So the studies on amino acid complexes in mixed solvents are still lacking. To know the solvent effects on thermodynamic parameters, we studied earlier the complexes Cu^{II}-glycinate⁹ and Cu^{II}-alanate¹⁰ in different t-butanol-water and glycerol-water mixtures at 25°. In continuation of that work, we report here the thermodynamic parameters of Cu^{II}-tyrosinate in water and enthalpies of formation of Cu^{II}-tyrosinate in different t-butanol-water and glycerol-water mixtures at 25°.

Results and Discussion

Since a small amount of Cu^{II} ion is reacted with a large

excess of tyrosine in the pH range 9.7-12.0, we get the enthalpy change for 1 : 2 type of complex⁴. Two reactions occur simultaneously,

where, HL stands for tyrosine. All other reactions such as the formation of CuL, have been reported to be negligible by Thornton and Skinner⁴ under the conditions of our experiments. From the total heat liberated (Q_1) we can get ΔH for reaction (1) after correction for liberation of heat (Q_2) due to the reaction (2) using the relation, $\Delta H = -Q/X$, where $Q (=Q_1 - Q_2)$ is the heat liberated (J) for X moles of the complex CuL₂ formed.

For different concentrations of Cu^{II} ion, we notice that ΔH is the same within experimental error over the pH range 9.7-12.0. Since we used fairly dilute solutions and all the Cu^{II} ions being complexed in the reaction, the experimental ΔH values were taken as ΔH° . The values of ΔH° of formation of Cu^{II}-tyrosinate so determined in water, glycerol-water and t-butanol-water are given in Table 1. The stability constant of Cu^{II}-tyrosinate in water was determined earlier by Letter and Bauman⁸. They also determined

TABLE 1-ENTHALPY CHANGE FOR $\text{Cu}^{2+} + 2\text{L}^- \rightarrow \text{CuL}_2$ IN t-BUTANOL-WATER AND GLYCEROL-WATER MEDIA AT 25°

Wt%	- ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
	t-Butanol-water	Glycerol-water
t-Butanol/Glycerol		
10	50.52 ± 0.07	53.99 ± 0.09
20	54.09 ± 0.15	56.40 ± 0.10
30	58.13 ± 0.18	55.67 ± 0.16
40	57.06 ± 0.20	52.44 ± 0.18
50	55.02 ± 0.21	51.06 ± 0.20

calorimetrically the enthalpy of formation of Cu^{II}-tyrosinate in aqueous medium at 25°; the value obtained is -46.32 kJ mol⁻¹. So our value (-46.36 kJ mol⁻¹ given in Fig. 1) is in very good agreement with that value. The value obtained by Gergely *et al.*⁶ (-52.30 kJ mol⁻¹) differs from this probably because they measured at 27°. Using the values of ΔG° given by Letter and Bauman⁸, ΔS° in water was calculated to be 128.82 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. Since ΔG° in mixed solvents are not available, ΔS° was not calculated.

**Present address : Department of Chemistry, Vidyasagar College, Calcutta-700 006.

Fig. 1 presents the plot of enthalpy of formation $-\Delta H^\circ$ (kJ mol^{-1}) against solvent-composition. Inspection of the figure reveals that $-\Delta H^\circ$ passes through a maximum around 30 wt% of t-butanol in t-butanol-water system and 20 wt% of glycerol in glycerol-water system. Similar behaviour was observed by us in the study of the formation of Cu^{II} -glycinate⁹ and Cu^{II} -alanate¹⁰ in the above mixed solvents; also in the formation of dipyH^+ and PhH^+ ¹¹, $[\text{Fe}(\text{dipy})_3]^{2+}$ ¹² and $[\text{Fe}(\text{Ph})_3]^{2+}$ ¹³. The maximum structuration of t-butanol-water mixtures at about 30 wt% agrees well with the observations of Pointud *et al.*¹⁴ in their study of the enthalpy of transfer of LiCl and HCl in t-butanol-water system. The maximum structuration model is also supported by some thermodynamic and spectroscopic arguments¹⁵.

Fig. 1. Plot of $-\Delta H^\circ$ against solvent composition.

Experimental

Glycerol¹⁶, t-butanol¹⁶ and copper sulphate⁹ were purified as described earlier. Tyrosine (E. Merck, G.R.) was dried at 110° for 8 h and then dissolved in NaOH solution to form sodium tyrosinate. Both the reacting solutions were taken in the same mixed solvent.

Perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide (AnalaR) were estimated in the usual way. All solutions were prepared with double-distilled water from an all-glass set-up.

The details of the calorimeter¹⁷ and some modifications¹⁰ have been reported earlier. For the measurement of the enthalpy change of Cu^{II} -tyrosinate in water, freshly prepared CuSO_4 solution ($3.0\text{--}3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; 5 ml) in HClO_4 was taken in a pyrex glass bulb and large excess of sodium tyrosinate ($4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; 250 ml) was taken in the Dewar flask. For the measurement of the enthalpy change of Cu^{II} -tyrosinate in t-butanol-water, concentrations of CuSO_4 were varied between 2 and $3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ while the concentration of tyrosine was $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, whereas in glycerol-water, concentrations of CuSO_4 were varied between 1.5 and $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and that of tyrosine $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. Both the solutions were taken in the same mixed solvent. The final pH of the solution was kept between 9.7 and 12.0. For each run, the concentration of tyrosine was always more than ten times the concentration of Cu^{II} ion.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their heartiest thanks to Prof. S. Aditya, Department of Chemical Technology, Calcutta University, for his guidance and interest in the work.

References

1. N. INGRI and L. G. SILLEN, *Acta Chim. Scand.*, 1962, **16**, 159.
2. I. G. SAYCE, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1397.
3. R. S. TOBIAS and M. YASUDA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 207.
4. A. C. R. THORNTON and H. A. SKINNER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1969, **65**, 2044.
5. W. F. STACK and H. A. SKINNER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 1136.
6. A. GERGELY, I. NAGYPAL and B. KIRALY, *Acta Chim. (Budapest)*, 1971, **68**, 285.
7. A. GERGELY and T. KISS, *Magy. Kem. Foly.*, 1975, **81**, 15.
8. J. E. LETTER, JR. and J. E. BAUMAN, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 443.
9. S. BANDYOPADHYAY and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 76.
10. S. BANDYOPADHYAY and S. ADITYA, *Int. J. Sc. Eng.*, 1984, **1**, 57.
11. S. BANDYOPADHYAY, A. K. MONDAL and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 467.
12. S. BANDYOPADHYAY, A. K. MONDAL and S. ADITYA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1982, **52**, 201.
13. A. K. MONDAL, S. BANDYOPADHYAY and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1390.
14. Y. POINTUD, J. P. MOREL and J. JULLIARD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1976, **80**, 2381.
15. E. K. BAUMGARTHER and G. ATKINSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 2336.
16. S. BANDYOPADHYAY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 1286.
17. S. C. LAHIRI, A. K. ROY and S. ADITYA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1976, **16**, 277.